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Front Cover

Front Cover: By Sgt Karl Byrne

For more Defence Forces photographs, checkout:
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Hello, and welcome our fifth issue of 2020, continuing with our 80th volume – in the historic milestone the *An Cosantóir* magazine has reached.

Due to the lack of events happening around the country because of Covid-19 we've replaced our *On Parade* pages with an *In Focus* piece by the Executive Committee of ARCO. The second *In Focus* piece by Capt (AR) Damien O'Herlihy, is about the Cavalry Club. *Vets News* features a nice piece about a wreath laying ceremony in Listowel, Co. Kerry for the Irish men and women who lost their lives in WWII.

Our first main feature, the second part of our EAS article, provided by *Signal Magazine*, by Comdt Declan Daly (Ret'd), finishes the article and gave us a very informative look at how the EAS programme evolved through the years.

In *Cyber Security*, by Dinos Kerigan-Kyrou, he gives us some invaluable information on how to protect our online existence during the Covid-19 pandemic. Dinos is responsible for the cyber security sector of the Joint Command & Staff Course. He is an instructor on NATO DEEP - the Defence Education Enhancement Programme - based at the Partnership for Peace Consortium of Defence Academies.

Ruairi de Barra remembers the tragic loss of L/Sea Michael Quinn DSM in *Nuestra Señora de Gardtoza*. This tragic story brings us back 30 years to a courageous attempt to rescue the stranded Spanish crew of the fishing vessel *Nuestra Señora*

de Gardtoza after their mayday call.

Moving on from tragedy, Part 2 of our *EUFOR Tchad/RCA Review* continues to look back at the African mission and the political and military aspects that effected the mission, Part 3 next month will complete the series.

In *COVID-19 and the WPS*, Lt Col Mary Carroll informs us of the Women, Peace and Security communities work during the current pandemic and also how WPS will move forward into the future.

Our *Tac-Aide* is a handy feature for the survivalist, with info on how 3 different ways to purify water, life saving information if you every find yourself in a drastic situation at home or overseas.

Lt Nicole Kelly looks back on her overseas trip to Mali in *The Welcome from the Malians has been Humbling*. Cpl Lee Coyle gives us an insight into the Joint Task Force which was based in the Mckee Bks gym for the period of its necessity.

There's plenty more to read in the magazine so please enjoy and of course we have our regulars, *Sport*, *Noticeboard*, *What I Do* and our competition which is running for a limited time and could see you win 1 of 5 unique handcrafted pens kindly provided to us by Bill Dooley of Curragh Pens, see page 4 for further details.

Many thanks to all our contributors, especially Ruairi Kavanagh of *Signal Magazine* for providing us with some of the articles featured in this issue of *An Cosantóir Magazine*.

Sgt Karl Byrne – (Stand-in) Editor

WRITING FOR AN COSANTÓIR

We are always looking for new content from readers of all ranks and units, both serving and retired, full-time or reserve. All material submitted should have a military related topic or be of interest to our readership. Articles should be submitted electronically by email or memory-stick. Written articles (hardcopy written on paper) are also accepted but may delay its use depending on the editorial timeline in which we receive it.

Short articles are from 300 - 700 words max per A4 page along with 3 - 5 photographs. Regular articles are 2 pages with 700 - 1400 words with 7 - 10 photographs to allow a suitable selection process. Larger articles are considered but may spread over 2 or 3 issues depending on its size.

The Following are key elements in a story:

- The Title - the headline of the story
- The Lead - the first sentence of the story
- The Nut Graph - this paragraph explains the news value of the story and usually comes after the lead
- The Body - this includes background information and supporting material
- The Ending - this is meant to give a logical and satisfactory conclusion to the story

Sending in photographs:

- Save as - jpeg/png format
- File size - no less than 2mb
- Resolution - 300 DPI / 72 DPI with a larger size is also sufficient
- It must include L/R rank, first and second names & who took the photograph

‘Defeating the Pandemic, Defending Our Critical Infrastructure, and Securing Cyberspace: Battles We Cannot Afford to Lose’

BY DINOS KERIGAN-KYROU

C OVID-19 has resulted in serious illness and loss of life across Ireland and the rest of the world. Working closely with our healthcare professionals, the Defence Forces have a critical and central role in the response to the pandemic.

Cyber security and the protection of our critical infrastructure may not appear as issues which are particularly relevant at this time. But they are crucial if we are to minimise economic harm, sustain recovery, and establish safe and effective infrastructure - including resilient medical infrastructure - for the long-term. Unfortunately, the time of such a pandemic is a period when those who want to cause harm online - and there are many of them - seek to take advantage and are at their most prolific.

Cyber security is the security of cyberspace - the online environment that directly affects everyone. Cyber security includes the protection of our personal, business, and organisational information. Your own personal cyber and information security cannot be separated from the security of the Defence Forces and the security of the State.

Many of the things we use every day in the home, and our vital critical infrastructure including factories, transport, supply chains, logistics, finance, energy, and medical and healthcare infrastructure is increasingly connected online. And every company and organisation in Ireland, including the Defence Forces, have moved increasingly to working online, including the use of video meetings, in a way that could not have been imagined just a few months ago.

The security of cyberspace directly affects the economic, and physical health and well-being of every single person in Ireland. But when our guard is down, and we are understandably focusing on other hugely important concerns, is when those that wish to cause harm have an unprecedented opportunity to do so. As US Admiral (ret'd) James Stavridis states: *“Much like the invisible*

enemy of coronavirus, cyberthreats can't be seen until they manifest themselves in the kinetic world. But the triple threat of criminal activity, national security risks and non-state hackers is becoming all too apparent during this pandemic. As more of the world's basic commerce communications and governance goes online - for the most part on unsecured, easily tapped platforms - the cybersphere becomes an increasingly target-rich environment."

GETTING THE FOUNDATIONS RIGHT

Your email is the gateway to all of your information. It's also the door through which a nefarious actor can target the Defence Forces. So use a unique password that you only use for your email. Use 'two-factor authentication' - 2FA. It will take you just minutes to set-up; all major email providers enable it. 2FA exponentially increases your cyber and information security - and therefore the security of the Defence Forces.

A 'phishing' email, which pretends to be from a trusted colleague or superior, is the number one way for a nefarious actor to gain access to your computer or the Defence Forces network. If an email appears suspect, even if you have already clicked on a link or opened a file, report it directly to CIS Corps or via the IKON portal. There will never be any blame for anyone reporting a possible cyber security problem, regardless of how caused.

Don't share the link to join video conferences outside your trusted network. Password protect these calls if you can, and have control over each person's entrance to the meeting. And if someone you don't know appears online question who exactly they are, especially if their camera is switched off.

Keep your computer software up to date. All Apple and Windows systems have free built-in antivirus software so make sure this is switched on, or speak with CIS Corps if you're not sure.

Be careful of any links sent to you by email or text over your phone. Just because the message says it's from your CO or sergeant, it does not mean it actually is. And never click a link claiming to be from your bank. If someone claiming to be your bank calls you to tell you about 'suspicious activity on your account' it will not be your bank. No matter how convincing they sound, hang-up the phone.

Be careful who you meet online and share personal information with. Cyber threats, blackmail, cyber extortion, or cyber stalking should always be reported to your Commanding Officer. Further information is available at National Cyber Security Centre Ireland at ncsc.gov.ie And critical information for keeping your family safe online can be found at cybersafeireland.org

Our cyber security can only be protected by every single person within our companies and organisations across the State being empowered to identify security challenges. And this is critical to defending the Defence Forces as we move to the 'New Normal' online environment in which we'll be working, to a greater or lesser extent, for years to come. It's only by working together across departments outside our normal structures and hierarchies to identify security challenges that we can effectively secure our critical infrastructure, our cyberspace, the Defence Forces, and ultimately the State during - and in the years that follow - the COVID-19 pandemic. ■

ABOUT THE AUTHOR

Dinos Kerigan-Kyrou is responsible for the cyber security sector of the Joint Command & Staff Course. He is an instructor on NATO DEEP - the Defence Education Enhancement Programme - based at the Partnership for Peace Consortium of Defence